

A Systematic Narrative Review of Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) in India

Shruti Rawal¹, Happy Agrawal², and Megha Choudhary³

Department of English, St. Xavier's College Jaipur, Rajasthan¹

Department of Business Administration, St. Xavier's College Jaipur, Rajasthan²

Government Polytechnic College, Tilak Nagar, Bhilwara, Rajasthan³

A key component of the Indian development framework is the centrally sponsored maternity benefit schemes. These schemes are developed to improve maternal and child health while providing support to women during pregnancy. The Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) is one such scheme, which provides conditional cash incentives upon early pregnancy registration, regular antenatal care visits, and institutional delivery. Though a vast number of studies have been conducted on the scheme's effectiveness, the findings are scattered across geographical contexts, sample demographics, and methodologies, providing a limited understanding. This article is a narrative synthesis of 35 studies published between 2017 and 2025, focusing on the maternal health services, implementation process, and equal access to the scheme. The synthesis reveals an increase in utilization of health services due to PMMVY, with an even higher uptake when implemented with programmes like National Health Mission, Janani Suraksha Yojana, and Integrated Child Development Services. Yet, limited awareness, administrative hurdles, digital exclusion, and perceived inadequacy of the benefit are seen as consistent barriers to its access. These are more prominent among marginalized women, such as women from tribal communities, migrant households, informal workers, and low-literacy groups. The article provides an overview of the scheme implementation by synthesizing studies across different contexts and identifies scope for future research and policy suggestions.

Keywords: Maternity benefit schemes, PMMVY, conditional cash incentive, maternal health services

The Indian social system has diverse cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic backgrounds. Many communities differ by caste, religion, language, and geographical region. This diversity creates challenges related to social injustice, gender inequality, and unequal access to basic necessities, which have shaped the development of our policies over decades (UNICEF India, 2026). The Indian policies, considering equity and social protection, aim to address the historical challenges experienced by marginalized groups, such as women, children, and socially excluded communities (UNICEF India, 2026). Institutions such as the Ministry of Women and Child Development are developed with an aim to design and implement programmes related to nutrition and child development, to protect rights and improve the well-being of these communities (Ministry of Women & Child Development, 2026). Such social policies respect

diversity while maintaining social justice and inclusive development.

An important part of India's development framework is the central government schemes. These schemes are centrally sponsored and central sector programmes that work for the social, health, and economic welfare of the country (List of schemes of the government of India, 2025). They follow national policies and also allow states to manage them according to their administrative capacities (Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation (MoSPI), 2023). These schemes cover various sectors such as health, education, women and child development, finance, and hence provide a multi-dimensional approach to support development.

The schemes support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as SDG 3 (Good Health & Well-being), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities). The National Nutrition Mission (POSHAN Abhiyaan), launched on March 8, 2018, in alignment with these goals, targets maternal and child nutrition outcomes through the use of technology, convergence and community involvement. It aims to reduce stunting, anemia and handle malnutrition (Mission POSHAN 2.0, 2025). Other health-focused schemes such as the National Health Mission (NHM), including conditional cash transfer programmes like the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY), focus on the health of mothers and newborns (Bakshi et al., 2024). They encourage institutional deliveries and better antenatal care to cover the health goals under SDG 3 (National Health Mission, 2025).

Within this network of welfare-oriented schemes rolled out by the Indian Government, the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) was implemented with the aim to improve maternal and child health (Department of Women & Child Development,

Author Note

¹Dr. Shruti Rawal, Department of English, St. Xavier's College Jaipur, Rajasthan

E-mail: shrutirawal@xscjpr.edu.in

²Dr. Happy Agrawal, Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, St. Xavier's College Jaipur, Rajasthan

E-mail: happyagrawal@xscjpr.edu.in

³Dr. Megha Choudhary, Government Polytechnic College, Tilak Nagar, Bhilwara, Rajasthan

E-mail: meghachoudhary@gmail.com

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Shruti Rawal, Department of English, St. Xavier's College Jaipur, Rajasthan

E-mail: shrutirawal@xscjpr.edu.in

Government of India, 2024). Launched on January 1, 2017, PMMVY is a conditional cash transfer scheme that provides financial assistance upon early pregnancy registration, complete antenatal care visits, and child immunization, thereby providing partial compensation for the wage loss during pregnancy and early motherhood (Department of Women & Child Development, 2024). The ICDS infrastructure and health facilities are used to implement the scheme, while direct fund transfer is used for the financial aid (Department of Women & Child Development, 2024; Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana, 2026).

Since the beginning, scholars have shown great interest in conducting several empirical studies, state-level evaluations, and qualitative assessments to understand different aspects of the scheme, including awareness and utilization patterns, implementation mechanisms, administrative challenges, and utilization of maternal health services. Studies from multiple regions have shown that PMMVY is related to an increase in early registration of pregnancy, greater utilization of antenatal care, and higher compliance with immunization visits (Banerjee et al., 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Shruthi, 2024). At the same time, low awareness among marginalized communities, the documentation process, digital exclusion, irregular installments, and unequally distributed frontline workers are identified as major barriers affecting the reach and effectiveness of the scheme (Kumar et al., 2024; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019; Sharma & Singh, 2025).

Though a huge amount of literature has focused on the scheme, there are still some gaps. Most of the studies focus on a particular state or on specific aspects like utilization or awareness, and are cross-sectional. This does not give a holistic understanding and also limits the generalization of findings. Many studies do not consider PMMVY's interaction with other centrally sponsored schemes and maternal and nutrition policies (Kumar et al., 2024). This makes it difficult for researchers and policymakers who want to understand the scheme's role within the Indian development system and its overall contribution to maternal and child health.

A systematic narrative synthesis combining findings across different policy evaluations, review papers and previous research will be helpful in developing a complete understanding of the design, implementation, and impact of PMMVY. Since the studies differ in their designs, sample characteristics, and analysis measures, narrative synthesis will be effective. The synthesis will be helpful in identifying the common patterns, regional variations, and research gaps. It will also give an understanding of how PMMVY works within the broader area of maternal health policies and centrally sponsored schemes.

A total of 35 studies published between 2017 and 2025 are used for this narrative synthesis. These include various government reports, policy analyses, and peer-reviewed articles, which covered centrally sponsored schemes rolled out by the Indian government, with PMMVY as the point of focus. The synthesis covers studies across different disciplines and geographical settings, giving an in-depth understanding of the scheme and its contribution to maternal and child health.

Rationale

Though extensive research has been carried out to assess different aspects of PMMVY, like awareness of the scheme, utilization of healthcare services, and its implementation at administrative levels,

they have rarely explained how the scheme works as a part of the overall healthcare system. Apart from this, most of the studies have a focus on short-term utilization indicators, which do not give information about the equity outcomes and implementation dynamics of the scheme. Evidence on how the scheme intersects with other complementary schemes is also limited. Policy design, frontline implementation, digital delivery mechanisms, and social determinants affect health outcomes, but their interaction has not been extensively studied. By synthesizing the findings across different study designs and regional contexts, the article attempts to provide a holistic understanding to improve future research and policy development.

Objectives of the Study

This narrative synthesis is performed to understand the maternity benefit schemes of India by inculcating existing research on the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY), with the following objectives:

- To understand how PMMVY functions in practice by combining studies on financial support, governance process, and social factors affecting the utilization of maternal healthcare services
- To identify structural and implementation barriers limiting the effectiveness of the scheme
- To understand equity implications by evaluating differential access and outcomes across demographic, socioeconomic and geographic contexts
- To understand PMMVY within the overall healthcare development system of India and its intersection with other schemes in determining maternal and nutritional health

Data Synthesis and Analysis

Research has shown a difference in the performance of PMMVY across states and social groups. Education, income, health literacy, caste, and migration status affect women's ability to access and benefit from the scheme in urban, rural, and tribal settings (Kumar & Shobana, 2023; Sharma & Singh, 2025). While the use of DBT for financial aid has improved transparency and reduced breakdowns, it has also created difficulties for women with poor digital literacy or limited banking access (Dhariwal et al., 2020). This synthesis reveals the following themes:

Utilization of Maternal Health Services

Many studies have found that the implementation of PMMVY has increased maternal health service utilization, early pregnancy registration, antenatal care visits, and institutional deliveries (Shaw & Dey, 2022; Taneja & Chowdhury, 2025). Studies using quantitative methods have reported higher utilization of ANC services among the scheme beneficiaries compared to non-beneficiaries (Katoch & Singh, 2025). This shift is especially seen when the scheme works with other schemes such as JSY and NHM (Banerjee et al., 2021; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Shruthi, 2024). Regression and quasi-experimental studies reveal the reinforcement effect of conditional cash transfer on service uptake, especially among low-income households (Kumar & Shobana, 2023).

The literature also shows irregularity in the use of these services. While early registration of pregnancy improved in urban slums, peri-urban settings, and migrant populations, drop-offs are observed in

later ANC visits and postnatal follow-up (Banerjee et al., 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2025). This shows that financial incentives alone may not be sufficient to maintain engagement.

Awareness, Information Gaps, and Social Determinants

Nearly all reviewed studies have shown awareness of PMMVY as an important factor in determining the implementation of the scheme. Studies using surveys and qualitative methods reveal poor knowledge of eligibility criteria, installment conditions, and application procedures among women with low education, informal employment, or limited interaction with frontline workers (Banate & Sonawane, 2024; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Shaw & Dey, 2022). Education, household income, and health literacy are found to be strong predictors, among other socio-economic factors, in awareness (Pandey, 2025; Sharma & Singh, 2025; Singh, 2022; Singha & Hazarika, 2024). Researchers using qualitative methods have shown that patriarchal decision-making structures and in-house power dynamics affect women's access to scheme benefits, even when they are aware (Bhattacharyya et al., 2025; Kumar et al., 2024; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019). Hence, social norms, along with the informational barriers, affect the impact of such maternity benefit schemes.

Governance, Frontline Workers and Implementation Challenges

A number of policy review reports and qualitative research have shown governance and implementation processes as another theme. Administrative delays, documentation formalities, and difficulties in inter-departmental coordination have been revealed by studies conducted at district and state levels (Sharma & Singh, 2025). The effectiveness of the scheme is also affected by work overload and poor training of frontline workers like ASHAs and Anganwadi workers, as they are the key mediators in the implementation process (Kumar et al., 2024; Shruthi et al., 2024; Shukla et al., 2023; Zuhda et al., 2025). Differences in administrative capacity, digital infrastructure, and prioritization by political parties cause differences in implementation process across states (Dhariwal et al., 2020; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019). This creates challenges for assessments at national level and shows the need for contextual analysis of government policies.

Digitalization, DBT, and Exclusion Risks

Transparency is improved after the introduction of Aadhaar-linked Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) systems for financial incentives. Yet, mixed evidence is seen on inclusivity. Multiple studies have found that rural women, migrants, and marginalized caste groups face challenges related to Aadhar card seeding, bank access, and digitalization (Banerjee et al., 2025; Falcao, 2025; Rasheed & Keshlata, 2023; Shruthi, 2024; Shukla et al., 2023). While the use of digital platforms helped fund disbursement in well-resourced settings, qualitative studies have shown that over-reliance on digital mechanisms without proper human facilitation reinforces the existing inequalities (Kumar et al., 2024; Sharma & Singh, 2025). The need to create a balance between efficiency and equity is seen as a common area of focus across the reviewed studies.

Adequacy of Benefits and Health Outcomes

Concerns regarding the adequacy of PMMVY benefits are consistently seen. In high-cost urban environments, the cash

incentive is perceived as insufficient to compensate for wage loss or improve nutrition (Banerjee et al., 2025; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019; Sharma & Singh, 2025). Studies focusing on nutrition have also shown limited impact on maternal diet and anemia, revealing poor association between cash transfers and change in diet behaviour (Jagannath & Chakravarthy, 2025; POSHAN Abhiyaan Reviews, 2025). This shows the importance of PMMVY to align with other nutrition programmes under ICDS and POSHAN 2.0 to attain sustained health goals (Rai et al., 2025).

Equity, Regional Variation, and Research Gaps

Another consistent area of concern was equity considerations. The access and impact of PMMVY differ by caste, class, education, and geographical location, with tribal, migrant, and adolescent women as underrepresented groups in both scheme coverage and study samples (Kaur & Bhat, 2022; Kumar et al., 2024; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019; Shruthi, 2024). While the scheme is implemented across the nation, the literature remains segmented, with few longitudinal and inter-state comparative studies (Banerjee et al., 2025; Joshi et al., 2025; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019).

Discussion

This narrative synthesis attempts to understand the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) within the socio-developmental context of the country. It shows that gender, class, caste, labour and state capacity together determine maternal health outcomes in India (Kaur & Bhat, 2022). The scheme cannot be evaluated without considering its interaction with the existing inequalities, which might be reinforced at times.

From a women-centred perspective, the reviewed literature reveals that pregnancy might lead to reduced mobility, economic vulnerability, and increased dependence on family members and frontline workers. The scheme is seen to be most effective when it fits with women's existing way of using health services, but if women have little autonomy, the conditions of the scheme can cause exclusion instead of engagement (Banerjee et al., 2025; Kumar et al., 2024). The findings are in line with the criticisms against policy designs that assume beneficiaries as independent, even in settings where family and patriarchy shape their choices.

Research also shows that PMMVY reinforces an instrumental view of women situating them as carriers for improved health statistics rather than recognizing their rights as citizens. By focusing on the conditions for the scheme's benefits, it makes them responsible for the outcomes, without addressing issues like quality health services, job security, and social protection (Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019). This approach can hide the difficulties women face in meeting programme requirements, especially those who are involved in informal jobs or live in areas with limited services (Gautam, 2020; Jeyashree, 2025).

The implementation of the scheme cannot be evaluated without considering the role of care labour. Frontline workers serve as key mediators and are involved in bringing the scheme into practice. At times, they are overburdened and lack institutional support and decision-making powers, causing unequal access to the scheme (Sharma & Singh, 2025; Shruthi et al., 2024; Zuhda et al., 2025). The implementation is often carried out by unpaid or underpaid female staff, which can lead to compromise in consistency and accountability (Kumar et al., 2024; Swain & Bakshi, 2024). Besides, since frontline workers are involved, social relations and negotiation

skills also affect the beneficiaries' access to benefits (Zuhda et al., 2025).

The use of digital systems through Aadhar-linked DBT mechanisms has increased administrative efficiency, but also created barriers for women with technological disadvantages (Behera, 2023; Shukla et al., 2023). While digitalization is often seen as a gender-neutral method to increase efficiency, the reviewed studies reveal that women's limited access to financial institutions, digital knowledge, and documentation requirements can create barriers (Falcao, 2025; Gautam, 2020; Rasheed & Keshlata, 2023). From a women-oriented policy lens, these findings show that technology does not automatically bring equality and instead, reinforce exclusion when women's differential access to resources is ignored (Sharma & Singh, 2025).

The limited impact of PMMVY on maternal health shows that cash incentive alone cannot bring change in diet behavior (Ramesh et al., 2025). Household responsibilities, family dynamics, and women's decision-making power are also involved in determining their nutrition and health outcomes (Bhattacharyya et al., 2025; Jagannath & Chakravarthy, 2025). Unless combined with access to nutrition services and livelihood support, the impact remains superficial.

The reviewed literature also shows the differential access of the scheme, with women belonging to tribal groups, migrants, and those involved in unstable jobs, being the least beneficial population. These differences are due to the misalignments between policy designs and women's real life situations, such as migration, missing documents, and poor access to institutions (Kumar et al., 2024; Sekher & Alagarajan, 2019). This creates concerns for the scheme's ability to achieve goals related to social justice and gender equality.

Literature on PMMVY shows that it is supportive, but has limited impact as a policy intervention within maternal health development in India. These limitations stem more due to the implementation methods that overlook women's social roles, household responsibilities, and differential resource access, and less due to its inadequacy as a maternity benefit scheme. To increase its impact, maternity benefits should be treated more as gender-sensitive entitlements, and not just conditional incentives (Bhutta et al., 2013). Better healthcare systems, trained frontline workers, and inclusive governance systems will also help in increasing its impact on the health and socio-economic status of women.

Limitations of the Study

While the narrative synthesis gives an overall understanding of the PMMVY implementation, it has some limitations. One of them is the nature of reviewed studies. A majority of the studies taken have cross-sectional designs, providing limited understanding of the scheme's long-term effects on health and nutrition. The relationship between participation in scheme and utilization of health services cannot be interpreted as its lasting impact (Banerjee et al., 2025; Shruthi, 2024; von Haaren & Klonner, 2020).

Although the scheme is implemented nationally, the literature is limited in its geographical coverage. Certain states and districts have been extensively studied, while others such as the North-Eastern region, central tribal belts, and high migration settings remain underexplored (Kumar et al., 2024). Hence, the findings cannot be generalized and may overlook the barriers faced by marginalized groups in specific regions.

Many studies have used surveys or interviews for data collection, which can lead to recall and social desirability bias. These biases can be seen in aspects such as awareness, compliance with the scheme's conditions, and perceived adequacy of benefits, where social norms and interactions with frontline workers may determine women's responses. This can give an overestimation or underestimation of the scheme's effectiveness.

The reviewed studies are more focused on the process and utilization indicators, and less on nutrition, mortality, psychological well-being, or child development. This gives a limited understanding of the scheme's socio-developmental impact and its contribution to women's long-term health and economic security in India.

Lastly, this review does not use any meta-analysis techniques. While narrative synthesis is an effective method given the different methodologies of the studies, it involves subjective interpretation in identifying themes and combining findings. Its effectiveness is dependent on the methodological rigor and contextual depth of the studies considered.

A Step Forward

This synthesis on PMMVY's impact provides a path to policy formations, program development, and future research. The suggestions are based on the patterns identified across the reviewed literature and aim to increase the impact of maternity benefit schemes in India.

Future policy formations should consider introducing region-specific awareness strategies to increase the scheme's access and enrollment among women. Proper training to frontline workers, increasing their role clarity, and providing them adequate incentives can increase their engagement and consequently, the scheme's outreach. Barriers related to knowledge gaps can be addressed by giving community-based information, making peer-support groups, and including scheme-related information as part of regular services women receive during pregnancy.

The future iterations of the scheme should use a more inclusive approach to digitalization. Exclusion due to Aadhar-linked systems can be addressed by simplifying the documentation process, increasing digital assistance at health and ICDS institutions, and providing a strong grievance redressal mechanism. The use of hybrid mode combining digital systems with human facilitation can help reduce inequalities due to poor technological knowledge.

Since PMMVY benefits are perceived as inadequate, future policies could use inflation - indexed benefit adjustments or regionally differentiated transfers address the variations in living costs and market conditions. Bringing flexibility in the conditions of the scheme can increase inclusivity without compromising accountability. Moreover, integrating PMMVY with other central government schemes would support a more holistic approach, aligning financial assistance with quality health services.

Future research could use longitudinal and mixed-method approaches to understand the long-term impact of PMMVY on maternal and child health in India. An intersectional analysis can also be conducted to assess the impact of the scheme across various underrepresented groups, such as adolescents, migrants, physically challenged women, and single mothers.

Conclusion

This narrative synthesis reveals the position of the Pradhan Mantri

Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY) in the Indian maternal health system. Within the socio-developmental context of women, the scheme has been effective in increasing pregnancy registration and utilization of maternal health services. Yet, mixed evidence is found on its impact on maternal nutrition and health outcomes. The synthesis found social and institutional contexts of women as major determinants of the scheme's effectiveness. Marginalized women, such as those involved in informal work, belonging to tribal communities, or low literacy, face barriers while accessing the benefits of the scheme. The scheme conditions, documentation requirements, and use of digital systems further increase difficulties in these contexts, limiting the access of the scheme. Providing proper training to frontline workers, increasing the scheme benefit amount, and alignment with other health and social development programmes can increase the scheme's effectiveness. Such changes in the maternity benefit schemes are essential for women's overall health and socio-economic development.

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